

Semi-Empirical Potential Surfaces for Some Mixed Alkali Trimers

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Potential energy surfaces, binding energy and equilibrium geometry of some mixed alkali trimers have been calculated by a semi-empirical method based on London's equation. Calculated potential surfaces are shown in the form of contour maps. At small internuclear distances, these surfaces are characterised by shallow potential wells extending into the entrance and exit valleys without an energy barrier. The trimers are found to be stable over a range of linear and bent configurations, the most stable configuration in each case being a linear one with the lighter alkali atom occupying the central position. This configuration is also symmetric in all cases excepting NaLiLi.

THE exchange reactions of alkali atoms with alkali dimers ($M' + M_2 \rightarrow M'M + M$, where M and M' may be the same or different atoms) are believed¹ to proceed via alkali trimers as the stable intermediates. A knowledge of the potential energy surfaces of these trimers is of considerable importance in order to help resolve the reaction dynamics of such reactions. Although there is experimental evidence² indicating that the trimers of all alkalis are stable molecules, nothing is known experimentally about their binding energy and geometry. No sufficient theoretical work has also been done on these systems. Ab initio calculations of Davis and Del Conde³ suggest that with respect to $Li + Li_2$, Li_3 is bound by 3 Kcal/mole in its linear configuration and by about 10 Kcal/mole in its isosceles triangular configuration. Semiempirical diatomics-in-molecules^{4,5} and valence bond^{6,7} calculations show that the trimers of Li and Na (M_3 and $M'M_2$ types) are stable by 4-11 Kcal/mole and those of K, Rb and Cs (M_3 type) by 2-4 Kcal/mole with respect to atom-dimer dissociation. Recently, molecular beam reactive scattering has been measured⁸ for the exchange reactions of Na with K_2 , Rb_2 and Cs_2 , and of K with Rb_2 . However, neither experimental nor theoretical information are as yet available for the potential energy surfaces of these reactions. The present status of ab initio calculations³ on alkali trimers seems to indicate that it is extremely difficult to apply these methods to the heavier trimers. It is, therefore, the purpose of the present investigation to calculate semi-empirically these potential surfaces and to deduce therefrom the binding energy and geometry of the relevant trimers. In order to compare our results with those of some similar calculations⁶, potential energy surfaces of $Li + Na_2$ and $Na + Li_2$ have also been calculated.

Results and Discussion

The method of calculation followed here is the same as given in details by Whitehead and Grice⁹. It makes use of the famous London equation⁹. The diatomic coulomb and exchange integrals occurring in this equation have been evaluated from the potential energy curves of the ground and triplet states of alkali dimers. The Morse¹⁰ and Rydberg¹¹ potentials have been used for the ground state (both of these potentials have been used for the sake of comparison) and a modified anti-Morse potential proposed by us¹² has been used for the triplet state. Experimental values of the potential parameters needed to evaluate these potentials are taken from Herzberg¹³. In cases where experimental values are not available, use has been made of the results of split-shell MO calculations of Sannigrahi and Noor Mohammad¹⁴.

The binding energy of the trimers has been calculated for a large number of linear and isosceles triangular configurations. In the latter configurations, the bond length of the reactant dimer has been kept fixed at its equilibrium value. Some typical potential energy surfaces of the linear trimers are shown in Figs. 1 to 3. As can be seen from these figures, all these surfaces exhibit a shallow potential well at small internuclear distances which extends into the entrance and exit valleys without an energy barrier. Moreover, for a given trimer $M'M_2$, the potential well is deeper (Figs. 1 and 2) when the lighter alkali atom occupies the central position. Variations of binding energy with respect to $M'M$ bond length of the trimers in their isosceles triangular configurations, are shown in Fig. 4. Calculated values of binding energy and equilibrium bond lengths of the trimers are given in the Table which includes also the

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results of Whitehead and Grice⁶ for $\text{Li} + \text{Na}_2$ and $\text{Na} + \text{Li}_2$ reactions. These results show that the mixed alkali trimers are stable not only with respect to separated atoms but also with respect to atom-dimer dissociation. Moreover, the most stable configuration in each case is a linear one with the lighter alkali atom occupying the central position. This configuration is also symmetric in all cases excepting NaLiLi . It is interesting to

Fig. 1. Potential energy surfaces of LiNaLi for linear configuration.

Fig. 2. Potential energy surfaces of LiLiNa for linear configuration.

Fig. 3. Potential energy surfaces of NaCsCs for linear configuration.

Fig. 4. Variation of binding energy with distance R of MMM' system for isosceles triangular configuration.

note in this connection that the Morse and Rydberg potentials in spite of their different analytical forms yield almost identical result both for binding energy and geometry.

For lack of relevant experimental data or accurate ab initio calculations on these systems it is not possible to test the quantitative accuracy of the present calculations. A comparison with the results of Whitehead and Grice⁶ which are obtained by the use of more accurate diatomic potentials, may be therefore of some interest. While comparing these results (see Table) with the present ones, we find that there is a very good agreement in bond lengths, but the binding energy values in some cases are over-estimated by about 2 Kcal/mole.

TABLE I : CALCULATED VALUES OF BINDING ENERGY (Δ) AND BOND LENGTHS (R_{AB}, R_{BC}) OF SOME MIXED ALKALI TRIMERS IN LINEAR AND ISOSCELES TRIANGULAR CONFIGURATIONS. ^a

A + BC \rightarrow ABC \rightarrow AB + C	$-\Delta$ (Kcal/mole)		R_{AB} (Å)		R_{BC} (Å)	
	Morse	Rydberg	Morse	Rydberg	Morse	Rydberg
Na + Li ₂ \rightarrow NaLiLi	10.80(89)	10.84	3.10(3.18)	3.10	2.90(2.79)	2.90
\rightarrow NaLi + Li	7.70(7.4)	7.72	3.80(3.74)	3.80	2.67(2.67)	2.67
Na + Li ₂ \rightarrow LiNaLi	8.71(6.8)	8.76	3.05(3.11)	3.05	3.05(3.11)	3.05
\rightarrow LiNa + Li	— —	—	— —	—	— —	—
Li + Na ₂ \rightarrow LiNaNa	5.99(4.2)	6.00	3.03(3.08)	3.00	3.22(3.39)	3.25
\rightarrow LiNa + Na	0.72(0.9)	0.72	3.80(3.74)	3.80	3.08(3.08)	3.08
Li + Na ₂ \rightarrow NaLiNa	7.64(5.7)	7.68	3.07(3.10)	3.10	3.07(3.10)	3.10
\rightarrow NaLi + Na	— —	—	— —	—	— —	—
Na + K ₂ \rightarrow NaKK	4.35	4.38	3.80	3.80	4.10	4.10
\rightarrow NaK + K	2.75	2.77	3.83	4.83	3.92	3.92
Na + K ₂ \rightarrow KNaK	6.19	6.23	3.91	3.93	3.91	3.93
\rightarrow KNa + K	— —	—	— —	—	—	—
Na + Rb ₂ \rightarrow NaRbRb	4.15	4.15	4.10	4.10	4.40	4.42
\rightarrow NaRb + Rb	2.63	2.63	5.05	5.05	4.33	4.33
Na + Rb ₂ \rightarrow RbNaRb	5.75	5.77	4.15	4.15	4.15	4.15
\rightarrow RbNa + Rb	—	—	—	—	—	—
Na + Cs ₂ \rightarrow NaCsCs	3.90	3.92	4.35	4.40	4.80	4.75
\rightarrow NaCs + Cs	2.50	2.50	6.90	6.88	4.66	4.66
Na + Cs ₂ \rightarrow CsNaCs	4.36	4.38	4.50	4.52	4.50	4.52
\rightarrow CsNa + Cs	—	—	—	—	—	—
K + Rb ₂ \rightarrow KRbRb	4.25	4.27	4.30	4.30	4.50	4.50
\rightarrow KRb + Rb	3.45	3.46	5.35	5.35	4.33	4.33
K + Rb ₂ \rightarrow RbKRb	4.61	4.65	4.40	4.40	4.40	4.40
\rightarrow RbK + Rb	—	—	—	—	—	—

^a The upper and lower value for each M'MM system corresponds to linear and isosceles triangular configurations respectively. Values in the parentheses refer to those of Whitehead and Grice. These authors used a value of 23.75 Kcal/mole for the binding energy of Li₂, whereas the value used by us is 24.21 Kcal/mole. The difference is the zero-point energy of Li₂. The binding energy values are with respect to atom-dimer dissociation.

These authors have, however, remarked that their calculations might underestimate the stability of alkali trimers. In view of the fact that both of these calculations are based on London's equation which involves many approximations, a rigorous quantitative comparison is not of much significance. It is, however, expected that the qualitative features of all possible alkali atom-dimer exchange reactions can be understood from the present type of calculations.

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